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Features of Regulatory and Legal Regulation of Land Relations During the Period of Martial Law

Автором здійснено ґрунтовний аналіз нормативно-правового регулювання земельних суспільних відносин в Україні у період дії воєнного часу. Складні часи для всіх, і реальність, в якій постійно перебуває наша країна, вимагає прийняття непростих рішень, в тому числі й щодо нормативно-правового регулювання земельними. Для забезпечення функціонування держави в умовах воєнного стану та мінімізації кризових явищ у різних сферах суспільних відносин було прийнято низку законодавчих змін. Не залишилася поза увагою і сфера земельних відносин. Земля завжди залишалася найціннішим активом будь якої держави, адже вона є основним фактором виробництва та запорукою економічного розвитку країни. В умовах воєнного стану регулювання земельних відносин відіграє важливу роль, оскільки впливає не лише на земельний та аграрний сектор, а й на безпеку країни в цілому. За час дії воєнного стану на нашій території до законів, що регулюють земельні відносини, неодноразово вносилися зміни. Деякі обмеження, запроваджені на початку дії особливого правового режиму, були пом'якшені законодавцем, а для інших правовідносин, що змінилися або виникли у зв'язку з війною, встановлювалися нові правила. Як бачимо, законодавець системно підійшов до регулювання земельних відносин в умовах воєнного стану, передбачивши низку спрощень для забезпечення функціонування аграрного сектору економіки та якнайшвидшого відновлення інфраструктури України, а також встановивши низку важливих обмежень. Водночас, метою цих обмежень була мінімізація зловживань, які могли б значно зрости за відсутності належного контролю в умовах воєнного стану. Залишається сподіватися, що незручності, спричинені запровадженими обмеженнями, а також воєнним станом, триватимуть недовго, і що нормативно-правова база для відновлення України прискорить усунення наслідків війни.

Ключові слова: земля, особливості, земельні відносини, режим воєнного стану, правове регулювання, нормативно-правове регулювання, аграрний сектор, землі сільськогосподарського призначення, регулювання земельних відносин.

The author has carried out a thorough analysis of the regulatory and legal regulation of land social relations in Ukraine during the period of wartime. Difficult times for everyone, and the reality in which our country constantly finds itself, requires making difficult decisions, including regarding regulatory and legal regulation of land. To ensure the functioning of the state under martial law and minimize crisis phenomena in various spheres of public relations, a number of legislative changes were adopted. The sphere of land relations was not left out of attention. Land has always remained the most valuable asset of any state, because it is the main factor of production and the key to the country's economic development. In martial law, the regulation of land relations plays an important role, as it affects not only the land and agricultural sectors, but also the security of the country as a whole. During the martial law in our territory, changes were repeatedly made to the laws regulating land relations. Some restrictions introduced at the beginning of the special legal regime were softened by the legislator, and new rules were established for other legal relations that changed or arose in connection with the war. As we can see, the legislator systematically approached the regulation of land relations under martial law, providing for a number of simplifications to ensure the functioning of the agrarian sector of the economy and the speedy restoration of Ukraine's infrastructure, as well as establishing a number of important restrictions. At the same time, the purpose of these restrictions was to minimize abuses, which could significantly increase in the absence of proper control under martial law. It remains to be hoped that the inconvenience caused by the

introduced restrictions, as well as martial law, will not last long, and that the regulatory and legal framework for the restoration of Ukraine will accelerate the elimination of the consequences of the war.

Keywords: *land, features, land relations, martial law regime, legal regulation, regulatory and legal regulation, agrarian sector, agricultural lands, regulation of land relations.*

Problem statement. During the period of martial law, the legislation regulating land relations has changed repeatedly. The legislator has already managed to weaken some of the restrictions introduced at the beginning of martial law, and for certain legal relations caused or modified by the war, he has provided for new regulation. Let us consider the main current and potential legislative changes in this area.

The full-scale invasion of the territory of Ukraine in February 2022 forever changed the course of not only the modern history of Ukraine, but also administrative and legal regulation in all spheres of public administration. Of course, these are difficult times for everyone, and the reality in which our country constantly finds itself requires making difficult decisions, including regarding regulatory and legal regulation of land. To ensure the functioning of the state under martial law and minimize crisis phenomena in various spheres of public relations, a number of legislative changes were adopted. The sphere of land relations was not left out of attention. Land has always remained the most valuable asset of any state, as it is the main factor of production and the key to the country's economic development. In conditions of martial law, the regulation of land relations plays an important role, as it affects not only the land and agricultural sectors, but also the security of the country as a whole.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The regulatory and legal regulation of land relations during martial law, which still continues on the territory of our state, is in constant change. The issues of maintaining, implementing, effectively ensuring and protecting land relations have repeatedly been raised in scientific discussions by various researchers in various areas of public administration, in particular: V.I. Andreytseva, G.I. Balyuk, I.G. Bukhtiyarova, M.I. Vasilyeva, O.V. Zygriy, S.M. Kravchenko, O.V. Kuzmenko, V.K. Kolpakov, M.V. Krasnova, K.V. Medvedeva, T.V. Morozovskaya, V.V. Nosik, I.D. Pastuk, R.A. Serbyn, O.G. Strelchenko, S.R. Tagieva and others.

The purpose of the article is to conduct a thorough analysis of the regulatory and legal

regulation, which is in constant transformation and requires continuous improvement.

Presentation of the main material of the study. The action of martial law and active military operations on the territory of Ukraine cause changes in regulatory and legal regulation in any sphere of public administration, including in the sphere of administrative and legal regulation of land relations. It should be noted that the main legislative codified act in the sphere of regulatory and legal regulation of land relations is the Land Code of Ukraine. Article 1 of the Land Code of Ukraine determines that land is the main national wealth, which is under special protection of the state [1]. Regulation of land relations, which are relations regarding the ownership, use and disposal of land, is one of the most urgent and important issues in our country. Russian invaders, in addition to the most valuable thing - human life and health, are trying to wipe out everything around us, thereby polluting the soil; landscapes and nature conservation objects are being violated, which became the topic of our study [2; 3; 4; 5; 6].

In 2011, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine issued the Order “On Approval of the Action Plan for Land Reform and the Creation of a Transparent Agricultural Land Market”, which gave rise to land reform in Ukraine, which lasted for more than 10 years and included the adoption of new legislative acts, a land moratorium and the long-awaited opening of the land market in 2021. After the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine, legislators adopted Law No. 2247-IX “On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine Regarding the Features of Regulation of Land Relations under Martial Law”, which will be described further [7].

We understand that land relations must be adapted to the conditions of martial law, and land is one of the most valuable resources, so it was necessary to regulate its use during the war. The explanation to the Law states that its purpose is to promptly lease land plots of state and municipal ownership for the placement of production facilities of enterprises relocated from the combat zone, without conducting land auctions with restrictions on lease terms, as well as providing land plots for the placement of facilities for the temporary stay of internally displaced

persons, the sustainable functioning of electricity supply networks, gas distribution, water supply, heat supply, sewage networks, electronic communication networks, and gas main pipeline facilities. However, it is worth noting that, in addition to the aforementioned innovations, the Law also introduced some changes to the procedure for the privatization of land plots [7].

The modern reality that arose in Ukraine under martial law required serious and rapid transformations in the current legislation in order to effectively regulate social relations. The field of land law was no exception. On April 7, 2022, Law No. 2145-IX “On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine Regarding the Creation of Conditions for Ensuring Food Security under Martial Law” came into force in Ukraine.

The purpose of this law is to improve certain procedures and simplify the procedure for acquiring rights to use agricultural lands under martial law for their effective use for conducting commercial agricultural production and ensuring the food security of our state. In particular, on the basis of Law No. 2145-IX, a number of agreements were renewed that related to the lease, sublease, emphyteusis, superficies and land easement of land plots, the term of use of which expired after the introduction of martial law, as well as agricultural land plots of both state and municipal property, unclaimed and unallocated land plots, land plots that are in private ownership [8].

Also, on the basis of Law No. 2145-IX, conditions and requirements were determined regarding the procedure for the formation of new land plots and the documentation on the basis of which such formation is carried out, the conditions for the storage of such documentation. In particular, now, in order to form a land plot for the purpose of transferring it for lease, it is not necessary to enter information about such a land plot into the State Land Cadastre (state registration) and assign it a cadastral number. Such formation is carried out on the basis of technical documentation on land management for land inventory, which must be approved by this body and developed by the relevant decision of the body authorized to transfer the land plot for lease. At the same time, such technical documentation cannot provide for the division or unification of land plots. In addition, the legislator establishes the right of the lessee, sublessee of agricultural land of any form with the right to transfer his right to lease or sublease to

another person for the purpose of using the land plot for a period of up to one year. Such a transfer is possible without the consent of the owner of the land plot on the basis of a contract (written) on the transfer of the right to use the land plot between the land user and the transferee. The corresponding contract is concluded in electronic form and is subject to state registration. The person to whom it was transferred must be notified of such a transfer of the right to lease or sublease by the lessor, and in the case of the transfer of the right to sublease - by the lessee. This notification must be made in writing and within five days from the date of state registration of the agreement on the transfer of land use rights. As for the land ownership and land use registration book, under martial law it must be maintained by the district military administration in electronic and paper forms [8].

On June 9, 2022, the Law of Ukraine No. 2247-IX “On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine Regarding the Peculiarities of Regulation of Land Relations under Martial Law” came into force, which changed the rules for regulating land relations during martial law and full-scale war.

The law was designed to simplify the lease of land plots of state and municipal property - primarily for the placement of production facilities of enterprises relocated (evacuated) from the combat zone, critical infrastructure facilities and the placement of facilities for the temporary stay of internally displaced persons. In particular, the document is aimed at ensuring the prompt placement of production facilities of enterprises that are relocated (evacuated) from the combat zone - without conducting land auctions with strict restrictions on lease terms. Such enterprises will be determined by a joint decision of two OVAs (regional military administrations) - the one from which the production facilities are relocated (evacuated) and the one to which they are moving. Establishment and change of purpose of land plots, as well as provision of land plots for lease for placement of production facilities of enterprises that are relocated (evacuated) from the combat zone, construction (expansion) of river ports (terminals), multimodal terminals and production and transshipment complexes will be carried out without associated costs and approved urban planning documentation on the basis of a reasoned conclusion of the authorized body for urban planning and architecture. At the same time, it is prohibited to use nature conservation areas, lands of the nature reserve fund and other nature conservation purposes, historical and

cultural purposes, lands of the water fund (except for the placement of river ports (terminals), as well as to violate restrictions on land use (including in the field of development) for such purposes [9].

The purpose of Law No. 2247-IX was primarily to introduce special rules for the ownership, use and disposal of land, which should ensure the most urgent and significant needs in land plots of entities that are of great importance for the national economy, the agricultural sector and citizens of Ukraine under martial law and establish a simplified system for establishing and changing the purpose of land plots, as well as leasing state and municipal land for the placement of production facilities of relocated enterprises, etc. [10].

It should be noted that on April 28, 2022, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on the Activities of Notaries and the Functioning of Unified and State Registers, the Holder of which is the Ministry of Justice, under Martial Law" No. 480 dated April 19, 2022, entered into force, which provided for significant changes in the implementation of land legal relations, in particular, for the period of martial law and within one month after its termination/cancellation, the following features: notarization of agreements on the alienation of real estate, mortgage agreements, powers of attorney for the right to dispose of real estate is carried out exclusively by notaries included in the List of Notaries by the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine; registration of real rights to real estate is carried out, in addition to notaries included in the List of Notaries, also by state registrars determined by the Ministry of Justice; Notarization of contracts for the alienation of real estate and the corresponding state registration of rights is prohibited until the expiration of one month from the date of state registration of the alienator's right of ownership of real estate (except, in particular, for the registration of inheritance); Notarization of contracts for the alienation of real estate, mortgages, establishment of trust ownership of real estate (including amendments or termination of such contracts) and the corresponding state registration of rights based on the power of attorney of the alienator/mortgagor is also prohibited; Notarization of contracts for the alienation of real estate, mortgages, establishment of trust ownership of real estate is carried out exclusively at the location of such property (with certain features for the city of Kyiv and the Kyiv region); State registration of

ownership of real estate in connection with the transfer of property into the ownership of a legal entity as a contribution (contribution of property to the authorized (compounded) capital (authorized fund)), as well as into the ownership of individuals and legal entities that have left the founders (participants) of a legal entity, is prohibited.

Changes were also made to access to information from the State Land Cadastre, in particular, on May 14, 2022, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "Some Issues of Maintaining and Functioning of the State Land Cadastre under Martial Law" No. 564 dated May 7, 2022 came into force, which determined the conditions for maintaining the State Land Cadastre during the martial law in Ukraine and one month from the date of its termination/cancellation. According to this Resolution, user access to the State Land Cadastre is suspended within the administrative-territorial units, the list of which is approved by the State Service for Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre in agreement with the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food. Such a list is determined taking into account the list of administrative-territorial units within which user access to unified and state registers is suspended, and which are located in the area of military (combat) operations or which are under temporary occupation, encirclement (blockade), as well as the list of territories where hostilities are (were) underway or temporarily occupied by armed formations of the Russian Federation. However, within the administrative-territorial units that are not included in this list, operations with the State Land Cadastre are ensured taking into account the following features: entering information (changes to information) into the State Land Cadastre is carried out exclusively by state cadastral registrars of the State Service for Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre and its territorial bodies, included in the list approved by the State Service for Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre in agreement with the Ministry of Agrarian Policy; providing access to the State Land Cadastre to users who had such access before February 24, 2022 is carried out by decision of the State Service for Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre on the basis of their applications. Providing access to new users occurs in the general procedure established by law; The provision of such information from the State Land Cadastre may also be carried out by administrators of administrative service centers or authorized officials of executive bodies of local self-government, in particular: a) extracts from the State

Land Cadastre about the object of the State Land Cadastre; b) certificates containing generalized information about lands (territories), in the form established by the Procedure for Maintaining the State Land Cadastre; and c) copies from the cartographic basis of the State Land Cadastre, cadastral map (plan); the use of information from the State Land Cadastre about the coordinates of the turning points of the boundaries of objects of the State Land Cadastre is allowed only to persons specified in the List of cadastral registrars, as well as to certain certified land surveyors and surveying engineers. Such information is not indicated in extracts from the State Land Cadastre, copies from the cartographic basis of the State Land Cadastre, copies of documents of the State Land Cadastre; The Public Cadastral Map will not function, the publication of information from the State Land Cadastre through the Public Cadastral Map is not carried out.

Additionally, for a similar period, on May 14, 2022, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "Some Issues of Regulation of Land Relations" No. 563 dated May 10, 2022 suspended the implementation of a pilot project, according to which developers of land management documentation would have been able to enter information into the State Land Cadastre independently.

Changes have also been made to the features of the use of agricultural lands. Thus, taking into account the need for martial law to simplify the procedure, land is being transferred for use for the sowing campaign, which was determined on April 7, 2022 upon the entry into force of the Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine on Creating Conditions for Ensuring Food Security under Martial Law" No. 2145-ІХ dated March 24, 2022. It provided for the following rules for the duration of the martial law regime: contracts for the use of agricultural land plots of all forms of ownership, the term of which expired during martial law, are automatically extended for one year without the parties' consent; landowners and land users are exempted from liability for failure to use land plots for their intended purpose; agricultural land plots of state and municipal ownership may be provided for use only for commercial agricultural production; Free privatization of land plots is prohibited; land auctions are not held for lease rights, emphyteusis, superficies for agricultural land plots of state and municipal ownership; permanent users of

agricultural land plots of state and municipal ownership may lease them to TSV for a period of up to one year; tenants, subtenants of agricultural land plots of all forms of ownership without the consent of the landowner may transfer their lease rights, sublease to other persons for a period of up to one year under contracts in electronic form; for TSV management, agricultural land plots of state and municipal ownership, as well as those remaining in collective ownership, undistributed and unclaimed land plots and land shares (shares) are leased for a period of up to one year under the following conditions: a) the amount of the rent does not exceed 8% of the normative monetary valuation of the land plot; b) the contract is concluded in electronic form and certified by qualified electronic signatures of the parties; c) the formation of a land plot for its lease is carried out without entering information into the State Land Registry and assigning it a cadastral number, based on technical documentation on inventory; d) the right to lease is not subject to state registration. Instead, the district military administration carries out state registration of the contract; e) the contract cannot be renewed, concluded for a new term and is terminated upon the expiration of the term for which it was concluded (even if martial law was terminated earlier); e) the lessee of the land plot does not have the preemptive right of the lessee to renew the contract or purchase the SG Plot, the rights to compensation for his own expenses for improving the land plot, transferring the SG Plot to sublease, establishing an easement, building on the SG Plot, changing its intended purpose, etc.

The legislator also did not leave the possibility of compensating for losses of owners/users of land plots caused by the war. Accordingly, on March 21, 2022, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On Approval of the Procedure for Determining Damage and Losses Inflicted on Ukraine as a Result of the Armed Aggression of the Russian Federation" No. 326 dated March 20, 2022 came into force. This Procedure provides for the possibility of determining damage and losses in Ukraine as a result of the armed aggression of the Russian Federation. In particular, the Procedure establishes the main indicators for assessing land fund losses, namely: actual costs for the reclamation of lands that were disturbed as a result of hostilities, construction, arrangement and maintenance of engineering and technical and fortification structures, fences, border signs, border clearings, communications for the arrangement

of the state border; losses caused to owners (land users) of agricultural land plots; costs of restoration of reclamation areas; costs of demining. Regional, Kyiv City State Administrations (during martial law - military administrations) will be responsible for determining damage and losses, which will be carried out on the basis of the methodology. The relevant methodology must be approved by order of the Ministry of Agrarian Policy, in consultation with the Ministry for Reintegration of Temporarily Occupied Territories of Ukraine within six months from the date of entry into force of the Order.

There have also been potential changes in land legislation. Thus, in order to provide and change the purpose of land plots for the placement of production facilities of enterprises that are being relocated (evacuated) from the combat zone, the placement of facilities for the temporary stay of internally displaced persons, agricultural production, sustainable functioning of gas transportation and gas distribution systems, water supply and drainage, heat production, and electronic communications, on May 12, 2022, the Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine Regarding the Features of Regulation of Land Relations under Martial Law" was adopted (draft law No. 7289 of April 15, 2022). The law proposes to provide for the possibility of: leasing land plots that are transferred to the communal ownership of territorial communities without state registration of the right of communal ownership to them; to lease land plots of state and municipal ownership without conducting land auctions (with the definition of certain transfer conditions in the lease agreement) for: a) placement of production facilities of enterprises relocated (evacuated) from the combat zone (including those of strategic importance for the economy and security of the state); b) placement of river ports (terminals) on the Danube River / multimodal terminals and production and transshipment complexes, if the State Service of Maritime and River Transport of Ukraine / Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine makes a decision on the expediency of their construction (expansion); c) placement of sea ports; d) construction of electricity supply networks, gas distribution, water supply, heat supply, sewage networks, electronic communication networks, and main gas pipeline facilities; e) TSV; to lease for TSV management agricultural land plots of state and municipal ownership that are not classified as lands for TSV management, without changing their intended purpose; transfer land plots of

communal property for permanent use to executive bodies of village, settlement, city councils for the placement of facilities for temporary residence of internally displaced persons ("IDPs"). At the same time, the transfer of land plots of state, communal property for such purposes on other property rights to individuals and legal entities is prohibited; place temporary structures, their complexes, engineering networks intended for temporary residence of IDPs on land plots of all categories of land and without changing their intended purpose. The exception is lands of the nature reserve fund and other nature protection, historical and cultural and forestry purposes; change the intended purpose of the land plot on the basis of a motivated conclusion of the authorized body for urban planning and architecture of the relevant council, in the absence of urban planning documentation at the local level; fail to comply with the rules of the ratio between the type of intended purpose of the land plot and the type of functional purpose of the territory in the case of construction for temporary residence of IDPs; unhindered and free access to land plots of all forms of ownership for structures responsible for servicing gas, water, and heat supply systems and electronic communications operators in order to quickly eliminate accidents.

Conclusions. Thus, the legislator has systematically approached the regulation of land relations under martial law, providing for both many simplifications to ensure the functioning of the agrarian sector of the economy and the accelerated restoration of Ukraine's infrastructure, as well as significant restrictions. At the same time, such restrictions serve the purpose of minimizing the number of abuses, which could significantly increase under martial law in the absence of proper control. Therefore, we hope that all the inconveniences caused by the forcibly imposed restrictions, like martial law, will not last long, and the established regulatory framework for the restoration of Ukraine will help accelerate the elimination of the consequences of the war. During the period of martial law in our territory, changes were repeatedly made to the laws regulating land relations. Some restrictions introduced at the beginning of the special legal regime were relaxed by the legislator, and for other legal relations that changed or arose in connection with the war, new rules were established. As we can see, the legislator systematically approached the regulation of land relations under martial law, providing for a number of simplifications to ensure the functioning of the

agrarian sector of the economy and the speedy restoration of Ukraine's infrastructure, as well as establishing a number of important restrictions. At the same time, the purpose of these restrictions was to minimize abuses, which could significantly increase in the absence of proper control under martial law. It

remains to be hoped that the inconvenience caused by the introduced restrictions, as well as martial law, will not last long, and that the regulatory and legal framework for the restoration of Ukraine will accelerate the elimination of the consequences of the war.

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